

QUICK PHOTO GUIDE TO THE *TMARUS* SPECIES FROM SOUTH AFRICA: 2

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DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., & LOTZ L.N. 2020. *The Thomisidae of South Africa (S-T)* South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide Part 3, Version 1: 1-79. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7513278>

1. *Tmarus africanus* Lessert, 1919

2. *Tmarus cameliformis* Millot, 1942

3. *Tmarus cancellatus* Thorell, 1899 (only male)

4. *Tmarus comellinii* Garcia-Neto, 1989

5. *Tmarus foliatus* Lessert, 1928

6. *Tmarus guineensis* Millot, 1942 (only male known)

7. *Tmarus longicaudatus* Millot, 1942

8. *Tmarus natalensis* Lessert, 1925 (only male)

9. *Tmarus planetarius* Simon, 1903

